

(RESEARCH ARTICLE)

Patient motivation, satisfaction and attitudes towards involvement in inter-professional collaborative practice: A cross-sectional study

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World Journal of Advanced Research and Reviews, 2023, 18(03), 226–233

Publication history: Received on 24 April 2023; revised on 03 June 2023; accepted on 05 June 2023

Article DOI: <https://doi.org/10.30574/wjarr.2023.18.3.1035>

Abstract

During hospital-based long-term rehabilitation programmes, particularly for patients with spinal cord injuries, healthcare providers must make sure those patients are motivated, satisfied, and have positive views towards inter-professional collaboration among the team members. If they do this, patients will have a higher chance of sticking to their treatment plan, completing prescribed drugs, and getting better health results will have a higher chance of adhering to their treatment plan, taking the therapy recommended, and getting better health results if they comply with this. In a developing nation like Bangladesh, there is still much to learn about how patients feel about their care, what motivates them, and how they see the team that works with them. The purpose of the study was to investigate the level of motivation, attitudes, and satisfaction of people with spinal cord injury towards interprofessional collaborative practice. Quantitative research was applied to achieve the objectives. The overall motivation and satisfaction level of the patient with SCI towards interdisciplinary teamwork was high, 83.35% and 84.2%. Similarly, the patient attitude toward the team was just above average. The study findings could improve the rehabilitation sector's collaboration level by addressing strengths and weaknesses.

Keywords: Inter-professional Collaborative Practice; Spinal Cord Injury; Inter-professional Team Member; Patient involvement

1 Introduction

Worldwide, Rehabilitation of chronic long-term disease¹ conditions such as spinal cord injury demands inter-professional collaborative practice to ease quick decision-making, ensure maximum care provision without unnecessary treatment errors, and reintegrate them into mainstream society.²⁻⁴ Bangladesh is a developing country with a large population. However, facilities in health care service need to be improved where health professionals have to work with limited resources. In this stage, the collaborative practice could be the best-suited model for the rehabilitation health sectors of this country to improve the equal chance of getting treatment by involving patients in decision-making. These approaches aim to improve patients' motivation, satisfaction, and attitudes toward the rehabilitation team's coordinated care.¹ Patient involvement in inter-professional collaborative practice is crucial for several reasons.

Firstly, it promotes patient-centered care, where healthcare providers actively engage patients in decision-making and treatment planning.⁵⁻⁷ Secondly, patient involvement leads to better health outcomes.⁵⁻⁸ Patients involved in collaborative care tend to have better adherence to treatment plans, better quality of life, and better patient satisfaction.⁶ Thirdly, patient involvement promotes transparency and improved communication between healthcare providers.⁹ When patients are present during inter-professional meetings or rounds, they can provide important information about their care or ask questions that mitigate misunderstandings or communication gaps.¹⁰ Overall,

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patient involvement is essential for inter-professional collaborative practice, and healthcare providers should strive to involve patients in all aspects of their care.⁵⁻¹⁰

Healthcare providers and policymakers have increasingly recognized the relationship between patient outcomes and the level of patient motivation, satisfaction, and attitude related to coordinated care.¹¹⁻¹² One critical factor that influences inter-professional collaborative practice success is patient motivation.¹³⁻¹⁵ Highly motivated patients are likelier to engage in their care, follow their care plan, and achieve desired outcomes.¹⁶⁻¹⁷ Patient satisfaction is another critical factor related to inter-professional collaborative practice.¹⁸ When patients are satisfied with their care, they are likelier to stick to their care plans, follow through on recommended treatments and have better health outcomes.¹⁹ Patients who feel disconnected or dissatisfied with their care may be more likely to miss appointments or neglect their health needs, resulting in poor outcomes and further declines in health.²⁰ Attitude is also an essential factor when it comes to inter-professional collaborative practice. Patients with a positive attitude towards their care, providers, and overall health are more likely to have better outcomes.²¹⁻²² On the other hand, patients who have a negative attitude may be resistant to following care recommendations and may be more likely to experience poorer outcomes.^{7,11-13} Ultimately, inter-professional collaborative practice is more effective when patients are motivated, satisfied, and have a positive attitude towards their care.^{13,15} However, more is needed to know the perspective of the patient with spinal cord injury regarding the team collaborative approach. This paper explores patient motivation, attitudes, and satisfaction with collaborative practice including the perception of collaborative team functioning from the perspective of a patient with a spinal cord injury.

2 Material and Methods

A cross-sectional study was employed to measure the patient motivation, attitudes, and satisfaction with collaborative practice including the perception of collaborative team functioning from the perspective of a patient with a spinal cord injury using a survey questionnaire. The study participants were admitted patients with spinal cord injuries at the Centre for the Rehabilitation of the Paralyzed inpatient unit. The inclusion criteria included patients with SCI who gave voluntary consent and had experience participating in at least three inter-professional collaborative meetings. The patients with cognitive impairment and a score below 18 in the Standardized Mini-Mental State Examination were excluded from the study. According to the estimation during the data collection period, there are one hundred and twenty patients with spinal cord injuries. All patients were the current study participants according to their availability and volunteer participation.

An Information sheet including details information on the study aims and objectives, study design, study duration, institute affiliation, the identity of the investigator, Participant's confidentiality, Participant's rights and responsibilities, potential risk, benefit, and further information related to the study, was prepared for participants to provide before taking informed consent. A written consent form was also ready for the participants to verify their understanding of the information sheet, awareness about the potential benefits and risks of the participants, and their volunteer participation with signature. So it was significant to take consent from those interested in participating in the study. Before starting the interview, signatures were obtained from each Participant on a consent form. If the participants are not literate, a thumbprint has been undertaken in the presence of their relative. A Patient Attitude, Motivation, and Satisfaction Scale were used to collect participant data.

The approval of the study protocol was taken from the Institutional Review Board (IRB) of the Bangladesh Health Professions Institute (BHPI). Written permission from the authorities of the specific unit of the Centre for the Rehabilitation of the Paralyzed (CRP) was provided to conduct the study.

Before data collection, a convenient schedule in consultation with the Participant was obtained to avoid interruption in the flow of the patient's treatment. At first, the eligible participants were informed about the contents of the consent form through an information sheet. Then participants were asked to complete a written consent form to ensure volunteer participation. Afterwards, participants were asked to complete a self-administrative questionnaire that may need 20-30 minutes to complete.

3 Results

Table 1 Socio-demographic Characteristics of Patients with Spinal Cord Injury

Variables	Frequency(n)	Percentage (%)
Age of the Participants		
15-25 years	38	29.2
26-35 years	44	33.8
36-45 years	29	22.3
46-55 years	14	10.8
56-65 years	5	3.8
<i>Mean± SD</i>	<i>33.31+11.61</i>	
Sex of the Participants		
Male	101	77.7
Female	29	22.3
Educational Qualifications		
Illiterate	25	19.2
PSC	31	23.8
SSC	48	36.9
HSC	8	6.2
Degree	11	8.5
B. Sc	7	5.4
Previous Occupation		
Farmer	28	21.5
Day labourer	27	20.8
Housewife	23	17.7
Business	15	11.5
Student	24	18.5
Service holder	13	10.0
Family's Monthly Income		
<10000 BDT	58	44.6
10000- 20000 BDT	17	13.1
> 20000 BDT	55	42.3
Type of Injury		
Tetraplegia	54	41.5
Paraplegia	76	58.5
Duration of Hospitalization		
Less than one month	29	22.3
One month- 2 months	60	46.2
Two-month- 3 month	41	31.5

The patient with spinal cord injury age ranged was 15- 65 years. Of 130 patients, it indicates most of the participants were between 26 and 35 years, and the minimum participants represent the 56- 65 age range. Most participants were men, among them 21.5% (n= 28) of the farmer. Among the others, 20.8% (n=5) of participants worked as day labourers. 17.7% (n=23) of women participants were working as a housewife. 11.5% (n=15) of the participants were business people, 18.5% (n=24) were students, and 10% (n=13) of the patient with SCI were involved in the job as service holders (Table 1). Most of the participants, about 36.9%, have completed the secondary school certificate examination. Of 130 number of Participant, most of the Participant's about 44.6% (n=58), had a family monthly income of less than 10000 BDT (Table 1).

Figure 1 Patient Motivation toward Participate in Inter-professional Collaborative Team Approach

The findings show that patients are generally positively motivated to participate in the interprofessional collaborative team approach. The patients polled appeared to be pretty motivated, as indicated by the mean score of 4.95. With a score of 5.36, "Participating in IPC Team Approach is important for patient care" has the highest rating. The item has been reported "Participate eagerly to relieve anxiety by sharing with the team" the lowest rating (4.71). This shows that although patients are generally driven to interact with the team, they could be less enthusiastic about sharing their anxiety.

Figure 2 Mean of Patient Attitude toward Functioning of IPC Team

Based on the given scores, the results show the average attitude score is 3.55, which indicates a modest level of attitude towards the IPC Team's performance, as seen by the patients. "Team able to meet patient's expectation of being cared for" (4.74) and "Team leader eases discussion without being authoritative" (4.78) are among the items that obtained substantially higher attitude scores. These results imply that patients' attitudes toward the team's capacity to provide the treatment they anticipate and the team leader's leadership style are generally good. However, the team dynamics and communication-related categories earned much lower attitude scores. Patients' responses to the statements "Team members respect each other's opinion" (2.41), "Team members listen to each other attentively" (2.41), and "Team member creates conflict before ending discussion" (2.41) suggest that they have negative attitudes of these components of the IPC Team's operation.

Figure 3 Patient Satisfaction toward Inter-professional Collaborative Team Functioning

The average level of patient satisfaction with the IPC team's performance is roughly 3.62, which indicates an acceptable level of patient satisfaction. Items like "Satisfied with their ability to assess the problem" (4.97), "Satisfied with their ability to prepare a care plan" (4.95), and "Satisfied with their ability to find out treatment outcome" (4.85) had higher satisfaction ratings. According to these results, patients are generally satisfied with the team's performance.

Figure 4 The overall mean score of Patients' Motivation, Attitudes and Satisfaction

The results indicate the overall mean scores for Patient Motivation, Satisfaction, and Attitude toward the IPC Team Approach. The average patient motivation for the IPC team approach is 4.96, indicating that patients are generally motivated to participate in the team approach. The average patient satisfaction with the IPC Team's performance is 3.62, which denotes a reasonable degree of satisfaction. The IPC team's performance is generally viewed with medium patient satisfaction. Although certain aspects, such as communication abilities, mutual respect, and conflict resolution, were recognised as needing improvement, there is still space to raise patient satisfaction and enhance the IPC team's overall performance. This shows that patients' opinions of the team's performance are marginally lower than their satisfaction levels.

4 Discussion

This study aimed to explore the current situation of inter-professional collaborative practice among the team members in a spinal cord injury rehabilitation centre from the perspectives of patients with spinal cord injuries. The study result revealed that the overall motivation and satisfaction level of the patient with SCI towards interdisciplinary teamwork was high, 83.35% and 84.2%.

The first objective of the study was to determine the level of patient's motivation towards IPC team approach. The study results indicate that patients are highly motivated to engage in the IPC team approach. Patient motivation plays a crucial role in the success of the IPC team approach. When motivated, patients participate actively in their care, more connected

with team members, improving treatment outcomes and overall satisfaction. The results show that patients know the need for cooperation and teamwork to achieve successful health outcomes. They understand that the team's aggregate knowledge can deliver thorough and efficient care. Their eagerness to fully participate in the team process is motivated by this understanding. Patients' readiness to consult the team and ask questions is another sign of their motivation. Patients who ask inquiries show they want to learn more about their illness and available treatments. They actively seek knowledge and information from the team members because they understand their participation and engagement can lead to better decisions and results. The integrative review by Davidson 2022 found that the more motivated patients were more connected with the team member for ensuring collaborative practice.

The second objective of the study was to determine the level attitude towards the team functioning. The findings indicate that patients have a mixed attitude towards the IPC Team's performance. On the one hand, patients show positive attitudes towards certain aspects, such as the team's ability to meet their expectations of being cared for and the team leader's facilitation of discussions. These findings suggest that patients have confidence in the team's capability to provide the desired level of care and appreciate a leadership style that promotes open and collaborative communication. These results highlight potential weaknesses in the IPC Team's operation that may affect patient satisfaction. Patients prefer a cohesive team atmosphere in which individuals respect one another's viewpoints and pay attention to one another. Providing high-quality patient care and effective teamwork depend on a positive team dynamic. Conflicts and poor communication can reduce patient satisfaction and give the impression that the team needs to perform at its best. According to a systematic review conducted by Kilpatrick et al. (2019), patients generally have a positive attitude toward IPCP. Patients perceived IPCP as more effective in addressing their health issues and providing better care coordination. Patients also reported feeling more involved in their care when healthcare professionals worked together. However, the review also found that several factors, such as the level of patient engagement, the timing and scope of IPCP, and the type of health condition, influence patient perception of IPCP.

The third objective of the study was to measure the level of satisfaction regarding the functioning of IPC team from the perspectives of the patient. The findings indicate a modest level of patient satisfaction with the performance of the IPC team. Several areas earned lower patient satisfaction ratings, although they expressed higher satisfaction with features including problem evaluation, care plan creation, and treatment outcome determination. These are communication abilities, respect for opinions, and teamwork in handling conflicts. Addressing these issues can increase patient satisfaction and improve the IPC team's overall performance. Another study by Metersky et al. (2016) explored patients' perspectives on inter-professional teamwork in primary care.⁸ The study found that patients valued the different perspectives and expertise that healthcare professionals brought to their care.⁸ Patients appreciated collaborative care that was personalized to their needs, involved active listening, and incorporated their preferences into their care plan.^{8,9} Patients also appreciated a coordinated approach from their healthcare team, with clear communication and consistent messaging.⁸

The fourth objective was to determine the overall motivation, satisfaction, and attitude are to the IPC team approach. Patients motivated to participate in the team process actively are aware of the value of cooperation. Although patient satisfaction levels are moderate, fixing problem areas can increase patient happiness and enhance the IPC team's overall performance. Positive attitudes can be attained by enhancing team dynamics and communication. Patients' attitudes reflect how they view the team's skills. The IPC team can deliver healthcare more patient-centred and efficiently by taking these aspects into account and dealing with them. A systematic review by Vahda et al. 2016 found that patients' satisfaction with collaborative teamwork is associated with improved clinical outcomes, such as reduced hospital length of stay and improved medication management.¹⁹ The review reported that patients valued good communication and effective collaboration among healthcare professionals, particularly in chronic illness management.¹⁹ Patients appreciated having multiple healthcare professionals involved in their care as long as the team worked together cohesively and communicated using clear and understandable language. An important consideration when assessing the efficacy of the team approach is patient satisfaction with the IPC team's performance. It gives valuable information about how well the team satisfies patient demands and expectations, eventually affecting their treatment. The study's findings show a moderate level of patient satisfaction, indicating that they are usually happy with some aspects of how the team is working.

5 Conclusion

The study offers a crystal clear idea that there is a collaboration between interdisciplinary team members, which is beneficial for the patient and also essential for the organization and care providers. In addition, collaboration within a team is effective and efficient regarding patient satisfaction and motivation and is a less time-consuming approach. Overall, research on patient-centred decision-making in inter-professional collaborative practice can have important implications for delivering high-quality, patient-centred care. By involving patients in the decision-making process,

clinicians can develop care plans that are better tailored to the patient's needs and preferences, leading to improved patient outcomes, reduced healthcare costs, and enhanced patient satisfaction.

Compliance with ethical standards

Acknowledgments

We are acknowledging the contribution of the participants.

Disclosure of Conflict of interest

We declared no conflict of interest.

Statement of ethical approval

The ethical committee of the Bangladesh Health Professions Institute approved this study.

Statement of informed consent

An information sheet with detailed information on rights, roles, risks, and benefits was provided to each Participant before data collection, and a signed consent form was obtained for each Participant.

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